

Authorship Guidelines - BeFRAIL

Porto in Times of Cholera and War: A Bioarchaeological Approach to Human Frailty

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BeFRAIL is a multidisciplinary project that overarches various disciplinary fields. It aims to inform and foster scientific development while contributing towards societal changes on issues related to human frailty and inequality in health and wealth, and how this can be inferred via contextual archaeological, historical and socio-cultural analysis. A crucial part of the *BeFRAIL* project is to publish and disseminate its research.

Since authorship is a major evaluation criterion for those in academia, and because we aim to support a collaborative, fair and transparent working environment, please consider the following guidelines to acknowledge each author's contribution according to their input on each specific output (e.g., manuscript, poster, oral presentation, other). Overall, authorship positioning will vary, be heterogeneous, and be based on engaging collaborative work.

These guidelines are not mandatory but should be considered good practice for those collaborating on the *BeFRAIL* project. They hope to support authorship acknowledgement and provide guidelines for author ordering.

Granting Authorship

Before considering a person as an author or co-author, ask yourself:

- 1) Was the person significantly involved in designing the study, collecting data, analysing the data or supervising the research?
- 2) Was the person involved in drafting or editing the manuscript?
- 3) Was the person responsible for the accuracy and integrity of all aspects of the research?
- 4) Did the person prior to including the name approve the final version of the manuscript for publication?

You should also consider this exercise before adding your name to any output.

Please keep in mind that some authors' profiles will not fit what is expected in academia. There may also be differences according to country, research environment, and university policy. Outputs may include non-academic contributors such as community members, professional workers, and others whose contributions should be named. In such cases, the authors' collective may attribute an Honorary Authorship, acknowledging that some sort of contribution was/is at play, even if viewed as minor (compared to the role of other contributors).

In cases where no contribution can be identified but some sort of recognition out of respect or gratitude is acknowledged; or where there has been some discussion leading to minor exchange of ideas, this person/entity must be mentioned in the acknowledgements section. In these cases, gifting authorship is unethical and may be viewed as research misconduct.

Planning Authorship from the Start

Each research output is expected to have a lead author/instigator, such as BeFRAIL PI, or a main representative of a project task. This person will invite fellows to contribute to the research output, or open a call invite for those wishing to collaborate. Those who respond positively must discuss their contribution before the output development starts. This recommendation applies to all research outputs, including a publication, a poster presentation, a conference presentation, or any other output.

This "kick-off" discussion must be initiated by the lead author/researcher and/or supervisor or principal investigator who will oversee the output development.

The lead person may allocate tasks and conceptualise the dissemination project (output), following the BeFRAIL overarching research goals, aims, and methodological design. The lead person will have to keep track of everyone's contribution. It may help to maintain focus on the main objective of the core project - BeFRAIL - which informs and fosters scientific development while contributing to societal changes and interpreting human frailty issues.

The key point to remember is that it takes a team to complete a project, and one needs to work together to accomplish the same goal — may it be a publication/porter/presentation (other). [COMMENT ok, I see you have info on first authors later]

Authors CRediT (Contributor Roles Taxonomy)

The following authorship guidelines were designed to foster a prolific research environment based on transparency and fairness. They are not a novelty and are based on a significant body of literature already addressing this topic (see some references below).

CRediT (Contributor Roles Taxonomy) has been used to identify the 14 roles mostly representative of those typically attributed to contributors/authors. Each addresses a contribution essential to the publication/output development. These should be used to support equitable and fair decision-making when ordering authors within the BeFRAIL project.

The CRediT Classification roles include (description was slightly adapted from the original and is ordered alphabetically):

Conceptualisation	Formulation of ideas, research goals, aims and methodological design used in output development and execution.
Literature search	Includes literature search and literature review, and management of references
Data curation	Management activities include annotating (producing metadata), cleaning, and maintaining research data for initial use and later reuse.
Formal analysis	Statistical or other formal techniques of analysis or synthesise data study. It also includes qualitative analysis or literature review in case of systematic bibliography analysis.
Funding acquisition	Acquisition of the financial support for the project leading to this output development
Investigation	Conducting the research and investigation process, performing the experiments, data/evidence collection, and interpretation.
Methodology	Development or design of the methodology to use in this output development
Project administration	Coordination of the research activity, its planning and execution. As well as site coordination responsibility when applicable.
Resources	Provide study materials (e.g., laboratory samples and supplies, instrumentation, computing resources, or other analysis tools).
Software	Programming and software development; designing computer programs; implementing computer code and supporting algorithms; and testing existing code components.
Supervision	Oversight and leadership responsibility for the research activity planning and execution.
Validation	Verification, whether as a part of the activity or separate, of the overall replication/reproducibility of results/experiments and other research outputs.
Visualization	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically visualization/data presentation.
Writing – original draft	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically writing the initial draft (including substantive translation).
Writing – review & editing	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work by those from the original research group, specifically critical review, commentary or revision – including pre- or post-publication stages.

CrediT (Contributor Roles Taxonomy) scoring assessment

BeFRAIL CRediT (Contributor Roles Taxonomy) scoring assessment aims to quantify each author's contribution based on their participation per assigned role. This score provides a mathematical approach to authors' ordering. This scoring system is an adaptation of Winston (1985).

Attribute to each role a weight based on its relevance to the overall output. This allows one to calculate each author's total contribution, ordering them from the most to the least contribution. The scoring system/role identification may be adapted per each output typology (e.g., publication/poster/presentation) aim and contributors. Per each output; 1) **First** consider which items will appear in the manuscript/poster/presentation - these items may include text, figures, tables, and most importantly, the conceptualization of the manuscript/poster/presentation (e.g., ideas/arguments, goals, aims, and methodological design), thinking on the overall roles/tasks associated with each; 2) **Second**, estimate the weight based on its relevance to the overall manuscript; 3) **Third**, determine how much, and if, each author will contribute to each of these roles/tasks. The **final score** will support in-between 1st and last author ordering.

Alternatively, rather than assigning a score to each paired role/author, the table (see below) matrix may be used only to identify the pair role/author, which can also be used in the decision-making process.

However, it is very important to note that the scoring system or role identification are mere guidelines; hence, the final order of authors may have some ranking flexibility. This may be particularly true in cases where honorary authors are included.

See below Table exemplifying with roles associated with authorship:

Roles associated with project (Manuscript/Poster/other):		Contributor Score - CS = Total Points / n° authors			
		TOTAL Points	XX	XX	XX
Conceptualisation	Formulation of ideas, research goals, aims and methodological design used in output development and execution.				
Literature search	Includes literature search and literature review, and management of references				
Data curation	Management activities include annotating (producing metadata), cleaning, and maintaining research data for initial use and later reuse.				
Formal analysis	Statistical or other formal techniques of analysis or synthesise data study. It also includes qualitative analysis or literature review in case of systematic bibliography analysis.				
Funding acquisition	Acquisition of the financial support for the project leading to this output development				
Investigation	Conducting the research and investigation process, performing the experiments, data/evidence collection, and interpretation.				
Methodology	Development or design of the methodology to use in this output development				
Project administration	Coordination of the research activity, its planning and execution. As well as site coordination responsibility when applicable.				
Resources	Provide study materials (e.g., laboratory samples and supplies, instrumentation, computing resources, or other analysis tools).				
Software	Programming and software development; designing computer programs; implementing computer code and supporting algorithms; and testing existing code components.				
Supervision	Oversight and leadership responsibility for the research activity planning and execution.				
Validation	Verification, whether as a part of the activity or separate, of the overall replication/reproducibility of results/experiments and other research outputs.				
Visualization	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically visualization/data presentation.				
Writing – original draft	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically writing the initial draft (including substantive translation).				
Writing – review & editing	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work by those from the original research group, specifically critical review, commentary or revision – including pre- or post-publication stages.				
FINAL SCORE		100			

This table was adapted from information available on [CRediT](#)—Contributor Roles Taxonomy and Winston (1985). You may download Excel [HERE](#) and add the necessary information, making the adaptations you feel are needed.

Ordering Authors

The following sections aim to further support decision-making alongside the CRediT (Contributor Roles Taxonomy) scoring. The first and last authors may be obvious most of the time; however, ordering in-between authors may not be so even when we have a score. Deciding on the order of authors requires honesty, transparency, and conscientious discussion. This is sometimes difficult as

unconscious bias may exist, and depending on one's career position, the priorities may be diverse: a senior researcher, a post-doc, a PhD student, a MSc student, a laboratory or a field technician will have different personal objectives when contributing to a project aiming for dissemination.

Corresponding Author

The corresponding author is the liaison between the institution/journal/event to which the output was submitted. This author receives all the updates (e.g., submission status, reviewer comments and decisions). It is often the principal investigator of the core project, or if decided otherwise, the first author or another author may fulfill this role.

First Author

The first author is the person who contributed the most to the work and primarily has written most of the paper, including study design, data collecting, data analysis, writing, or other tasks. Note that a joint first or senior authorship may exist. That being the case a footnote may be added to the author listing stating precisely that: e.g. "X and Y should be considered joint first author" or "X and Y should be considered joint senior author." However, this may depend on the journal/format targeted. Due to BeFRAIL's multidisciplinary nature, these situations may occur and will have to be discussed in detail.

Last Author

The last author is usually the principal investigator of the core project or supervisor(s) who has a high level of responsibility and who oversees the project and final output. Note that this person receives much of the credit when the project is successful but will also receive criticism when something goes wrong. Due to BeFRAIL's multidisciplinary, similar to 1st authors, more than one last author in a manuscript.

In-Between Authors

The in-between authors are usually listed according to their contribution, from the most to the most minor contributors. However, it is also possible to order these authors according to their seniority in the group or the degree of difficulty needed to carry out a specific part of an output. An alternative would be to order authors based on alphabetical order; however, this should be discouraged as it is not representative of the actual contribution of each author.

To support fair decision-making when ordering in-between authors the CRediT (Contributor Roles Taxonomy) scoring assessment was set (see above). It aims to quantify each author's contribution based on the author's contribution per assigned role and provides a mathematical approach to authors' ordering.

As stated above, in cases where no contribution can be identified but some sort of recognition out of respect, gratitude, and/or aligned research interest leading to minor exchange of ideas, this person/entity must be mentioned in the acknowledgements section. Gifting authorship in these cases is unethical and may be viewed as research misconduct.

Whatever the approach, the fundamental is to always discuss and research a consensual agreement.

Alphabetical ordering has been used in the past, but it is not the most transparent in terms of workload.

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